

Paracompactness and dense subsets

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Abstract. In this paper we continue the study of some covering properties related with paracompactness: A -paracompactness in a subset, paracompactness in a subset, A -paracompactness with respect to a subset, and paracompactness with respect to a subset, and we obtain some characterizations of compactness.

Keywords: paracompactness; coverings; dense subsets; α -paracompact subsets.

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Introduction

Lupiañez and Outerelo [6] introduced some covering properties related with paracompactness, which allow us to characterize paracompact, compact, pseudocompact, lightly compact, collectionwise normal with respect to paracompact and closed sets, and countably compact spaces.

In this paper, we study these properties for a dense subset and we obtain some characterizations of compactness.

The following definitions are used in this paper:

Definition 1 [1] *A subset E of a topological space X is said to be α -paracompact in X if every covering of E by open subsets of X has a refinement by open subsets of X locally finite in X , which covers E .*

Definition 2 [7] *A subset E of a topological space X is said to be normal (regular) in X , if E and each closed (one-point) subset of X , non-intersecting E , have disjoint open neighbourhoods.*

Definition 3 [2] A collection of sets $\mathcal{G}$ of a topological space X is locally finite with respect to a set S if there exists an open set $V(S)$ containing S such that $V(S) \cap G \neq \emptyset$ for only finitely many members $G \in \mathcal{G}$.

Definition 4. [6] Let X be a topological space and let E be a subset of X .

1) We say that X is A -paracompact in E if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite in E (i.e.: in every point of E)

2) We say that X is paracompact in E if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U$ for some $U \in \mathcal{U}$ has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite in E .

3) We say that X is A -paracompact with respect to E if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite with respect to E .

4) We say that X is paracompact with respect to E if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U$ for some $U \in \mathcal{U}$ has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite with respect to E .

Remark 1 [6]

1) If X is A -paracompact in (with respect to) E , then X is A -paracompact in (with respect to) F for every $F \subset E$.

2) We have:

(a) X A -paracompact in $E \Rightarrow X$ paracompact in E (The converse is false)

(b) X A -paracompact with respect to $E \Rightarrow X$ A -paracompact in E (The converse is false)

(c) X paracompact with respect to $E \Rightarrow X$ paracompact in E (This implication is an equivalence if X is regular and T_0)

(d) X A -paracompact with respect to $E \Rightarrow X$ paracompact with respect to E (The converse is false)

3) A topological space X is paracompact, if and only if is A -paracompact in X .

A topological space X is compact, if and only if, is A -paracompact with respect to X .

1. General results.

Proposition 1.1. Let X be a topological space and E be a subset of X . Then, we have that, for each closed C of X such that $C \cap E = \emptyset$ and for each covering of C by open subsets of X there exists a refinement by open subsets of X locally finite in E , which covers C , if and only if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U_0$ for some $U_0 \in \mathcal{U}$ has an open refinement which is locally finite in E .

Proof. We have that $X \setminus U_0$ is closed of X and disjoint with E , then there exists an open refinement $\mathcal{U}^*$ of $\mathcal{U}$, locally finite in E , which covers $X \setminus U_0$, and $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{U}^* \cup \{U_0\}$ is an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}$ which is locally finite in E .

Conversely, if C is closed and disjoint with E and $\mathcal{U}^*$ is a covering of C by open subsets of X , we have that $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{U}^* \cup \{X \setminus C\}$ is an open covering of X and has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite in E . The $\mathcal{V}^* = \{V \in \mathcal{V} \mid V \not\subset X \setminus C\}$ is an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}^*$, locally finite in E , which covers C . ■

Corollary 1.2. *Let X be a topological space and E be a subset of X . The following properties are equivalent:*

- (a) X is paracompact in E .
- (b) For each closed set $C \subset X \setminus E$, we have that C is α -paracompact with respect to E (i.e. the sufficient condition for last Proposition)

Proposition 1.3. *Let X be a T_1 space and E be a subset of X . The following properties are equivalent:*

- (a) X is paracompact in E (or paracompact with respect to E) and E is regular in X .
- (b) E is normal in X .

Proof. (a) $\Rightarrow$ (b) If F is a closed subset of X non-intersecting E , then for each $y \in F$ there is an open neighbourhood V^y such that $\overline{V^y} \cap E = \emptyset$. Thus $\mathcal{U} = \{V^y \mid y \in F\} \cup \{X \setminus F\}$ is an open covering of X with $E \subset X \setminus F \in \mathcal{U}$. By the hypothesis there exists an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ which is locally finite in E . Finally $st(F, \mathcal{V})$ and $X \setminus st(F, \mathcal{V})$ are disjoint open neighbourhoods for F and E respectively.

(b) $\Rightarrow$ (a). Since X is T_1 , E is regular in X . For each open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U_0$ for some $U_0 \in \mathcal{U}$, we have that there is an open G with $E \subset G \subset \overline{G} \subset U_0$. Thus, $\mathcal{V} = \{U_0\} \cup \{V \setminus \overline{G} \mid V \in \mathcal{U}, V \setminus \overline{G} \neq \emptyset\}$ is an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}$ which is locally finite with respect to E (and, clearly "in E "). ■

2. Dense subsets

There exist two early concepts of paracompactness relative to dense subsets: the d -paracompactness and the D_p spaces.

We will show some relations between these notions and our four concepts of paracompactness type.

Definición 5. [3] *A space X is called d -paracompact if every open covering of X has an open refinement which is locally finite on some dense subset of X .*

Definition 6. [5] A space X is D_p if there exists an α -paracompact dense subset of X .

Remark 2. A D_p space may fail to be d -paracompact.

To show this, we use the following space [5]:

Let $X = \{a_n | n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ where $a_n \neq a_m$ if $m \neq n$, and let $A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$. Let each point of A be isolated, and let $\{\{a_n\} \cup A\}$ a base of neighbourhoods at a_n , for each $n \geq 4$. Then, the set A is α -paracompact and dense in X . But X is not d -paracompact because $\mathcal{U} = \{\{a_n\} \cup A | n \geq 4\}$ is an open covering of X which has not an open refinement which is locally finite on some dense subset of X (since all dense subset of X contains A).

Proposition 2.1 A space X is d -paracompact if and only if every open covering of X has an open refinement which is locally finite on some dense open subset of X .

Proof. If $\mathcal{V}$ is an open refinement of $\mathcal{U}$ which is locally finite on some dense subset D , then for each $x \in D$ there exists an open neighbourhood U^x which meets only finitely members of $\mathcal{V}$. Thus $D \subset \bigcup_{x \in D} U^x = U$ which is open and dense in X and $\mathcal{V}$ is locally finite in U . ■

Remark 3. If X is a regular space and E is α -paracompact dense in X , then X is the only open set which contains E

(Because every α -paracompact subset of a regular space is normal in X).

Remark 4. A d -paracompact space may fail to be D_p .

(Indeed, each D_p regular space is paracompact [5], but there exists a Tychonoff d -paracompact space which is not metacompact [3]).

Proposition 2.2. Let X be a topological space and E be a dense subset in X . Then, X is A -paracompact with respect to E if and only if X is compact.

Proof. If $\mathcal{U}$ is an open covering of X , there exists an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite with respect to E , i.e. there exists an open set W containing E such that W meet only $V_1, \dots, V_r \in \mathcal{V}$. Since E is dense in X , we have that $\mathcal{V} = \{V_1, \dots, V_r\}$, and it is a finite refinement of $\mathcal{U}$. Then X is compact. ■

Remark 5. If X is A -paracompact in some dense subset, then X is d -paracompact.

Proposition 2.3. Let X be a topological space and let E be a dense subset of X . The following properties are equivalent:

- (a) X is paracompact with respect to E .
- (b) For each open subset U containing E , we have that $X \setminus U$ is compact.

- (c) For each closed subset C contained in $X \setminus E$ we have that C is compact.
 (d) For each open subset U containing E , we have that $Fr(U)$ is compact.

Proof. Firstly X is paracompact with respect to E if and only if, for each open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U_0$ for some $U_0 \in \mathcal{U}$, there is an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ and an open subset W containing E such that meets only finitely many members of $\mathcal{V}$. Since W is dense, this is equivalent to the existence of a finite open refinement (or a finite subcovering) for each open covering of X such that E is contained in some member of it.

(a) $\Rightarrow$ (b). If X is paracompact with respect to E , and U_0 is an open subset containing E , for each covering $\mathcal{U}'$ of $X \setminus U_0$ for open sets of X , the family $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{U}' \cup \{U_0\}$ is an open covering of X . Then, there is a finite subcovering $\mathcal{V}$, and $\mathcal{V}' = \mathcal{V} \cap \mathcal{U}'$ is a finite subcovering of $\mathcal{U}'$.

(b) $\Rightarrow$ (a). For each open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U_0$ for some $U_0 \in \mathcal{U}$, we have that $X \setminus U_0$ is compact, then exists a finite subfamily $\mathcal{U}'$ of $\mathcal{U}$ which covers $X \setminus U_0$. Thus, $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{U}' \cup \{U_0\}$ is a finite subcovering of $\mathcal{U}$.

(b) $\Leftrightarrow$ (d). if $\mathcal{U}$ is an open subset containing the dense subset E , we have that $X \setminus U = \emptyset$ and $Fr(U) = X \setminus U$. ■

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